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Increasing the Human Development Index Through the Rural Community Literacy Improvement Program

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Abstract

The Human Development Index (HDI) can be increased in various ways, one of which is the community literacy improvement program. Literacy and literacy, cultural and civic literacy, numeracy literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy and scientific literacy are proven and highly effective in promoting the efforts to increase the Human Development Index. The six basic literacy are not only effectively applied to the world of formal education, but can be actualized in society in general. This study involved 56 communities representing each hamlet in one village determined by purposive sampling technique with certain criteria. The results of this study indicate that improving literacy, cultural and civic literacy, numeracy literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy and scientific literacy are proven to increase the Community Development Index. Improving literacy skills is carried out by providing various kinds of basic training according to community needs. The basic training provided can stimulate the community to be more concerned with developments in the surrounding environment.

Keywords: Human Development Index, Literacy, Indonesia

1. Introduction

In the last period, the Human Development Index (HDI) of the Province of North continued to increase from year to year. The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) noted that in 2021 the Human Development Index of North Sumatra was at 72.00, an increase of 0.23 points from the previous year's 71.77. Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), the Human Development Index ranks of North Sumatra's 15th on a national scale. Within the scope of the North Sumatra Province, the Community Development Index of Labuhanbatu Regency is ranked 7th out of 33 Regencies in North Sumatra. As shown in the following table:

Table 1: Human Development Index

No	City District	Human Development Index (New Method)		
		2019	2020	2021
1	North Sumatra	71,74	71,77	72,00

2	Nias	61,65	61,93	62,74
3	Mandailing Natal	66,52	66,79	67,19
4	South Tapanuli	69,75	70,12	70,33
5	Tapanuli Tengah	68,86	69,23	69,61
6	North Tapanuli	73,33	73,47	73,76
7	Toba Samosir	74,92	75,16	75,39
8	Labuhan Batu	71,94	72,01	72,09
9	Asahan	69,92	70,29	70,49
10	Simalungun	72,98	73,25	73,40
11	Dairi	71,42	71,57	71,84
12	Karo	74,25	74,43	74,83
13	Deli Serdang	75,43	75,44	75,53
14	Langkat	70,76	71,00	71,35
15	South Nias	61,59	61,89	62,35
16	Humbang Hasundutan	68,83	68,87	69,41
17	Pakpak Bharat	67,47	67,59	67,94
18	Samosir	70,55	70,63	70,83
19	Serdang Bedagai	70,21	70,24	70,56
20	Batu Bara	68,35	68,36	68,58
21	Padang Lawas Utara	69,29	69,85	70,11
22	Padang Lawas	68,16	68,25	68,64
23	South Labuhanbatu	71,39	71,40	71,69
24	North Labuanbatu	71,43	71,61	71,87
25	Nias Utara	61,98	62,36	62,82
26	Nias Barat	61,14	61,51	61,99
27	Sibolga	73,41	73,63	73,94
28	Tanjungbalai	68,51	68,65	68,94
29	Pematangsiantar	78,57	78,75	79,17
30	Tebing Tinggi	75,08	75,17	75,42
31	Medan	80,97	80,98	81,21
32	Binjai	75,89	75,89	76,01
33	Padangsidempuan	75,06	75,22	75,48
34	Gunungsitoli	69,30	69,31	69,61

Source: North Sumatra BPS data, 2022

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the increase in the human development index in Labuhanbatu Regency only experienced a slight increase, namely an average of 0.07%. Starting from this, various programs to increase the human development index are things that must remain the attention of all groups. The human development index figure at the district level is certainly strongly influenced by the level of development index of each sub-district in the district, then the level of the human development index at the sub-district level is certainly influenced by the community development index of each village in the sub-district area.

Various research results and community service have shown that increasing the community development index can be started from the village with various methods and training. As the results of research conducted by (Melliana & Zain, 2013) suggest that increasing the human development index can be done by increasing the school participation rate (APS), quantity of health facilities and infrastructure, percentage of households with access to clean water, labor force participation rate (TPAK), and GRDP per capita. From these findings, there are the most basic things about various ways of increasing the community development index, namely employment and per capita GRDP where this factor is one of the indicators of people's life expectancy.

Increasing the community development index will be easier to do if the community has maximum economic resilience, there is life expectancy and the creation of mature community economic resource management,

increased knowledge related to the management of economic resources and the creation of various new financial sources for the community.

The national literacy movement is a milestone in the creation of an equitable increase in knowledge for the community. Today the literacy movement is no longer only focused on the school level and other levels of education. The literacy movement is currently targeting various levels of society, even rural communities. Village communities must be more proactive and concerned with the times. A developed society must have sufficient knowledge in managing and improving their standard of living economically. Literacy and well-being are two things that are interconnected. People or nations who study hard (literate) will surely achieve prosperity. Prosperity can be seen from two sides, namely physical prosperity and inner prosperity. Therefore, the program to increase the community development index will be carried out through rural community improvement programs which include, among others, reading and writing literacy (Sari, 2020), cultural and civic literacy (Rokhmawan & Firmansyah, 2017), numeracy literacy (White, 2010), financial literacy (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2011), scientific literacy (Holbrook & Rannikmae, 2009) and digital literacy (Martin & Grudziecki, 2006).

2. Literature Review

2.1 Human Development Index

Development is defined as an activity in an effort to improve the welfare of the community in various aspects of life which is carried out in a planned and sustainable manner by utilizing and taking into account the capabilities of resources, information and advances in science and technology, as well as paying attention to social developments (Bappenas & Dunia, 1999)

The human development index (HDI) is one of the measuring tools that can be used to assess the quality of human development, both in terms of its impact on human physical conditions (health and welfare) and non-physical ones (education) (Melliana & Zain, 2013). Development that has an impact on the physical condition of the community, for example, is reflected in the life expectancy and purchasing power of the community, while the non-physical impact can be seen in the quality of public education.

The Human Development Index is a measure to see the impact of regional development performance which has very broad dimensions, because it shows the quality of the population of an area in terms of life expectancy, education, and decent living standards (Novitasari & Khikmah, 2019). The Human Development Index is a composite index that is calculated as the average of three indices that describe the basic human ability to expand choices, namely the life expectancy index, the education index, and the decent standard of living index of the Central Statistics Agency (BPS, 2008).

2.2 Literacy

Literacy and well-being are basically two things that are interconnected. People or nations who study diligently (literate) will surely achieve prosperity (Febriyanti, 2020). Prosperity can be seen from two sides, namely physical and spiritual prosperity (Faroji, 2019). Prosperity is related to fulfilling life needs, maintaining health, and having material that exceeds the minimum standard requirements so that you can save and invest, while inner prosperity is related to feeling happy, happy, safe, peaceful, and peaceful (Rasyidah, 2019). Reading is one aspect of literacy activities (Hakim, 2021). People who read a lot will feel well. Minimum welfare in the inner context, for example getting inner satisfaction, peace of mind, and increasing insight or knowledge.

Literacy is the ability to read and write. The UNESCO expert meeting in Paris Prancil hinted at the broader meaning of literacy. In this context, literacy is no longer only related to reading and writing, but includes the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, calculate and use various printed and written materials related to various contexts. Literacy also involves a continuum of learning that allows an individual /

individual to achieve goals, develop his knowledge and potential, and participate fully in society and the wider organization (Harjono, 2018); (Keefe & Copeland, 2011); (Koltay, 2011); (Hastings et al., 2013).

3. Method

The research method is carried out starting from identifying the problem and then conducting an initial measurement of the level of the human development index from a literacy perspective such as literacy, cultural and civic literacy, numeracy literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy and scientific literacy. Measurement using interview techniques and filling out questionnaires that have been prepared (Sugiyono, 2017). The research sample was determined by purposive sampling method (Sugiyono, 2017). The sample in this study was taken evenly, namely the hamlet heads of 14 hamlets in Tanjung Medan Village, West Bilah District, North Sumatra, with 3 residents who were considered capable and understood what was being studied. So that the total sample in this study amounted to 56 people. The research method carried out can be described in the following flow chart:

Figure 1: Research Implementation Methods

3. Results and Discussions

The results of the implementation of this research will be described below in accordance with the steps or methods of carrying out the research carried out. In parsing respondents' answers, the categorization formula is used (Azwar, 2010) which are grouped into 3 categories, namely high, medium and low with the following formula:

Table 2: Three Tier Categorization

Formula	Category
$X \leq (\mu - 1\sigma)$	Low
$(\mu - 1\sigma) < X \leq (\mu + 1\sigma)$	Medium
$X > (\mu + 1\sigma)$	High

Source : Azwar 2010

3.1 Results of Measurement of Human Development Index. Initial Stage (Pretest)

The initial HDI measurement was carried out by giving a number of questions and statements to the respondents to be filled in and answered according to their abilities and knowledge. The results of the initial HDI measurements were obtained as follows :

a. The result of reading and writing literacy measurement

The implementation of the literacy pretest was carried out in order to see the literacy level of the community. From the results of the pretest, it was found that the highest score was 48 and the lowest score was 30. The standard deviation was 4.547 and the mean was 40.02.

Table 3: Categorization of Literacy Literacy Pretest

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 45$	High	7
2	$35 < X \leq 45$	Medium	36
3	$X \leq 35$	Low	13
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

b. Results of measuring cultural literacy and citizenship

The implementation of the cultural literacy and citizenship pretest was carried out in order to see the level of cultural literacy and citizenship of the community. From the results of the pretest, it was found that the highest value was 59 and the lowest value was 33. The standard deviation was 5.548 and the mean was 48.20.

Table 4: Categorization of Cultural Literacy and Citizenship Pretest

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 54$	High	11
2	$42 < X \leq 54$	Medium	36
3	$X \leq 42$	Low	9
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

c. Numerical literacy measurement results

The implementation of the numeracy literacy pretest was carried out in order to see the level of community literacy literacy. From the results of the pretest, it was found that the highest value was 39 and the lowest value was 21. The standard deviation was 3.405 and the mean was 31.70.

Table 5: Numerical Literacy Pretest Categorization

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 35$	High	4
2	$27 < X \leq 35$	Medium	47
3	$X \leq 27$	Low	5
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

d. Financial literacy measurement results

The implementation of the financial literacy pretest was carried out in order to see the level of public financial literacy. From the results of the pretest, it was found that the highest value was 70 and the lowest value was 40. The standard deviation was 8.909 and the mean was 52.45.

Table 6: Categorization of Financial Literacy Pretest

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
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1	$X > 61$	High	12
2	$43 < X \leq 61$	Medium	35
3	$X \leq 43$	Low	9
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

e. Digital literacy measurement results

The digital literacy pretest was carried out in order to see the level of digital literacy of the community. From the results of the pretest, it was found that the highest value was 56 and the lowest value was 30. The standard deviation was 5.512 and the mean was 40.05.

Table 7: Digital Literacy Pretest Categorization

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 46$	High	6
2	$34 < X \leq 46$	Medium	44
3	$X \leq 34$	Low	6
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

f. Scientific literacy measurement results

The scientific literacy pretest was carried out in order to see the scientific literacy level of the community. From the results of the pretest, it was found that the highest score was 70 and the lowest value was 43. The standard deviation was 7.269 and the mean was 58.70.

Table 8: Categorization of Science Literacy Pretest

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 65$	High	7
2	$51 < X \leq 65$	Medium	36
3	$X \leq 51$	Low	13
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

3.2 Identification of Availability of Literacy Books in Each Hamlet as a Source of Knowledge for Village Communities

Based on the results of identification and interviews conducted with each hamlet head and representative community that there are no books related to literacy such as literacy, cultural and civic literacy, numeracy literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy and scientific literacy in their hamlet. Books related to literacy are only available at the Village Head Office (Village Library) in a limited number, these books are obtained from donations from the Regional Library and Archives Service which are only related to certain programs or technologies. So that people really expect the availability of reading materials in each hamlet to make it easier for people to read in order to gain knowledge that can help improve community literacy.

3.3 Implementation of Training Activities to Improve the Community Development Index

In order to increase the HDI of the village community, various types of training were carried out for the community, especially the sample in the study. There are various types of training carried out by presenting several resource persons who have the ability in the field to be trained. The training is related to literacy, cultural and civic literacy, numeracy literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy and scientific literacy.

3.4 The results of the measurement of the Community Development Index. Final Stage (Posttest)

The measurement of the Community Development Index of rural communities is carried out after carrying out various types of training activities related to literacy, cultural and civic literacy, numeracy literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy and scientific literacy within a period of 8 months starting from February 2022 to September 2022.

a. Reading Literacy Measurement Results

The implementation of the literacy literacy posttest was carried out in order to see the literacy level of the community. In improving the literacy of the community, activities / training on proposal preparation are carried out, both proposals for activities for an event and the preparation of grant proposals. In addition, various discussions were held on increasing interest in reading in the village community. From the results of the posttest, it was found that the highest value was 49 and the lowest value was 34. The standard deviation was 4.157 and the mean was 42.68.

Table 9: Categorization of Posttest Literacy Read and Write

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 46$	High	11
2	$38 < X \leq 46$	Medium	36
3	$X \leq 38$	Low	9
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

b. Results of Measurement of Cultural Literacy and Citizenship

The implementation of the posttest of cultural literacy and citizenship is carried out in order to see the level of cultural literacy and citizenship of the community. In improving the cultural literacy and citizenship skills of the community, various activities/trainings on Nasyid and Albarzanji readings which are the culture and local wisdom of the village community are carried out as well as training on making bulletin boards in each hamlet with the aim of making it easier for the community to get the latest information both from the village government and nationally. It is also intended that the community is more concerned with the development of information and the latest laws and regulations that are directly related to the village community. From the results of the posttest, it was found that the highest value was 59 and the lowest value was 37. The standard deviation was 4.832 and the mean was 51.88.

Table 10: Categorization of Posttest Cultural Literacy and Citizenship

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 56$	High	16
2	$47 < X \leq 56$	Medium	34
3	$X \leq 47$	Low	6
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

c. Numerical Literacy Measurement Results

The implementation of the numeracy literacy posttest is carried out in order to see the level of literacy in the community. In improving the numeracy literacy skills of rural communities, activities/training on land area calculation are carried out for the application of fertilization of agricultural land and tax calculations. This is intended so that the community better understands how to effectively apply fertilizer to agricultural land which is the source of income for the majority of rural communities and better understands the obligations of rural communities to the state in the form of tax payments. From the results of the posttest, it was found that the highest value was 39 and the lowest value was 23. The standard deviation was 3.038 and the mean was 31.93.

Table 12: Numerical Literacy Posttest Categorization

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 34$	High	14
2	$28 < X \leq 34$	Medium	38

3	$X \leq 28$	Low	4
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

d. Financial literacy measurement results

The implementation of the financial literacy posttest was carried out in order to see the level of public financial literacy. In order to improve the financial literacy of rural communities, activities / training for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises are carried out which are focused on making various kinds of products that have economic value to serve as a new source of income, while also being given training on the formation of Small, Micro and Medium Enterprises as a means of distributing community products. The community is also given banking and investment training to stimulate the public on the importance of a safe new source of capital for their business. From the results of the posttest, it was found that the highest value was 73 and the lowest value was 45. The standard deviation was 7.549 and the mean was 61.34.

Table 13: Categorization of Financial Literacy Posttest

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 68$	High	15
2	$52 < X \leq 68$	Medium	34
3	$X \leq 52$	Low	7
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

e. Digital Literacy Measurement Results

The implementation of the digital literacy posttest is carried out in order to see the level of digital literacy of the community. In improving digital literacy skills, village communities are given training in designing and creating village websites that aim to help promote village and village community businesses digitally (Digital Marketing). Furthermore, socialization of wise reading on social media aims to provide an understanding of the importance of information and be wiser in filtering the existing information. Subsequent training relates to computerized financial reporting for Small, Micro and Medium Enterprises to make it easier for the public to control their business performance. From the posttest results, it was found that the highest value was 58 and the lowest value was 34. The standard deviation was 5.259 and the mean was 48.29.

Table 14: Digital Literacy Posttest Categorization

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
1	$X > 53$	High	9
2	$43 < X \leq 53$	Medium	42
3	$X \leq 43$	Low	5
Amount			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

f. Scientific Literacy Measurement Results

The implementation of the scientific literacy posttest was carried out in order to see the level of scientific literacy of the community. In improving the scientific literacy skills of rural communities, training on freshwater fish farming is carried out as a solution and a new source of income for the community by considering the availability of natural resources that are suitable for freshwater fish farming. Another training that was carried out was training on the manufacture of organic fertilizer for the community as a solution in maintaining rubber plantations and community oil palm plantations, so that people no longer depended on chemical fertilizers whose prices were increasing. From the results of the posttest, it was found that the highest value was 73 and the lowest value was 47. The standard deviation was 7.038 and the mean was 61.68.

Table 15: Categorization of Science Literacy Posttest

No	Average Score	Category	Amount
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1	$X > 68$	High	12
2	$54 < X \leq 68$	Medium	35
3	$X \leq 54$	Low	9
Total			56

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

The comparison of pretest and posttest scores is the comparison between the scores before the training and the scores after the training related to literacy literacy, cultural literacy and citizenship, numeracy literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy and scientific literacy within a period of 8 months starting from February 2022 until September 2022. The comparison can be seen in the following table:

Table 16: Comparison of the Number of People in each Literacy Pretest and Posttest

Literacy Type	Category	Pretest	Posttest	Information
Literacy Read Write	High	7	11	The mean pretest value is 40.02 and the mean posttest is 42.68
	Medium	36	36	
	Low	13	9	
Cultural Literacy and Citizenship	High	11	16	The mean pretest value is 48.20 and the posttest mean value is 51.88
	Medium	36	34	
	Low	9	6	
Numerical Literacy	High	4	14	The mean value of the pretest is 31.70 and the mean value of the posttest is 31.93
	Medium	47	38	
	Low	5	4	
Financial Literacy	High	12	15	The mean value of the pretest is 52.45 and the mean value of the posttest is 61.34
	Medium	35	34	
	Low	9	7	
Digital Literacy	High	6	9	The mean value of the pretest is 40.05 and the mean value of the posttest is 48.29
	Medium	44	42	
	Low	6	5	
Science Literacy	High	7	12	The mean pretest value is 58.70 and the mean posttest is 61.68
	Medium	36	35	
	Low	13	9	

Source: Data Processed By SPSS For Windows 20

From the comparison table of pretest and posttest scores above, it can be seen that the value of each in each literacy has increased in the high category. Literacy reading and writing increased the number in the high category by 4 people and decreased the number of medium and low categories. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by (Chrystomo et al., 2020) which states that literacy training can improve the Human Development Index. In cultural literacy and citizenship there was an increase in the number in the high category by 5 people, and a decrease in the number in the medium and low categories. This result is in line with the results proposed by (Herwina, 2020). In numeracy literacy, the number in the high category also increased by 10 people and the number in the medium and low categories decreased. This proves that the increase in the Human Development Index with numeracy literacy training can be actualized. This result is in line with what was stated (Afria, 2021). Furthermore, there was an increase in financial literacy in the high category by three people and a decrease in the number in the medium and low categories. This indicates that the training provided on financial literacy can effectively increase the Human Development Index. This is in line with the results of the research/environment conducted (Ary et al., 2021). In digital literacy, there was an increase in the number in the high category by 3 people and a decrease in the number in the medium and low categories. This means that the effectiveness of increasing digital literacy skills can increase the Human Development Index. This is in line with what was stated (Nurulita, 2021); (Marsono et al., 2021) in his research related to digital literacy in improving the Human Development Index. Furthermore, in scientific literacy there was also an increase in the number in the high category by 5 people and a decrease in the number in the medium and low categories. This proves that an increase in the Human Development Index can be done with a program to increase community literacy (Atika et al., 2019); (Statistik, 2020).

So it can be concluded that the program to increase community literacy is very effective in increasing the human development index, especially the people of Tanjung Medan Village, West Bar District, North Sumatra. The community literacy improvement program is intended to involve the six basic literacys, namely literacy, cultural and civic literacy, numeracy literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy and scientific literacy.

4. Conclusion

Based on what has been stated previously regarding the research objectives, it can be concluded that the increase in the human development index can be carried out with programs to increase community literacy, both literacy literacy, cultural literacy and citizenship, numeracy literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy and scientific literacy. The six basic literacys can be actualized to the community as one of the bases for the formation and improvement of the community development index from the village level. Based on this, the literacy improvement program should not only emphasize education but must be able to reach the village community evenly. Future research is expected to consider a wider number of samples and a more varied sample selection in order to obtain more comprehensive information and data

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